

Quantum Stochastic Energy Conservation

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Classical statistical equilibrium appears to be based on a no-flow situation with a balance of pressure (including $-dV/dx$ in the case of a potential present). It may be noted, however, that like quantum mechanics, a single particle has different probabilities of being at one x versus another. Furthermore, the Maxwell-Boltzmann, Fermi-Dirac and Bose-Einstein distributions may be obtained using reaction balance which is linked to conservation of energy i.e. $g(f(e_i))g(f(e_j)) = g(f(e_l))g(f(e_k))$ where $e_i + e_j = e_l + e_k = e$. Taking \ln of the former expression and linking to the latter yields $f(e_i)$, the probability distribution. $g=1$ for the MB case, $f(e)/(1-f(e_i))$ for the FD and $f(e)/(1+f(e_i))$ for the BE.

In classical mechanics, one has the conservation equation: $p(x) \cdot p(x)/2m + V(x) = E$. In quantum bound systems one has: $KE(ave)(x) + V(x) = E$ which appears to be very similar, although it is based on ensemble averages and there is a momentum distribution $P(p/x)$ at each x . A question which arises is: What is the "conservation of energy" equation for a particular p of the $P(p/x)$ distribution? In this note, we argue the "potential" term associated with a component $p \cdot p/2m$ is related to the part of the potential which contributes to the "creation" of p . In particular, we consider $V(x) = \text{Sum over } k V(k) \exp(ikx)$ where each k term renders a kick of momentum k . One may create a momentum p using k and $p-k$ for each value of k . We further argue that: $p \cdot p/2m P(p/x) + \text{contributing portion of } V(x) = E P(p/x)$ ((1)) for all p . Thus, in quantum equilibrium, which involves a flow, there is a "constant E " type of equation i.e. ((1)), different in form but similar in idea, to that of classical statistical mechanical equilibrium. In previous notes, we referred to this as cycling, but in this note we wish to consider it in terms of dynamics. We further note that in both classical statistical mechanics and quantum mechanics, the energy-probability p equation makes use of the overall average energy which is bT for the classical case and E for the quantum. (b is constant)

Classical Statistical Mechanics

Classical statistical mechanical equilibrium involves no flow, so there is pressure balance including $-dV/dx$ from a potential. This yields a density as a function of x . If one considers a single particle, it has different probabilities to be at one x versus another like in quantum mechanics. Unlike quantum mechanics, there are two body collisions between different particles which drive the equilibrium. Interestingly, however, both the classical statistical mechanical case and quantum bound states are based on linking momentum/energy probability to an energy equation for p as we argue later in this note. Furthermore, both sets of p are linked to an overall average energy, bT temperature in the classical statistical mechanical case and E average in the quantum.

Quantum Conservation of Energy

The time-independent Schrodinger equation seems to imply average conservation of energy at each point x i.e.:

$$[\text{Sum over } p \quad p^*p/2m a(p) \exp(ipx)] /W(x) + V(x) = E \quad ((2))$$

One may ask: What conservation of energy equation applies to a component p ? Given that $\text{Sum over } p P(p/x) = 1$, where $P(p/x) = a(p)\exp(ipx)/W(x)$, One may rewrite ((2)) as:

$$\text{Sum over } p \{ p^*p/2m a(p) \exp(ipx)/W(x) + V(x)P(p/x) - EP(p/x)\} = 0 \quad ((3))$$

This suggests an average potential contribution from $V(x)$ of $V(x)P(p/x)$, but $V(x)$ is already an average and so one may question such an approach. This begs the question: What portion of $V(x)$ is associated with $p^*p/2m$? First, we consider $p^*p/2m P(p/x)$ which is the average kinetic energy associated with momentum p . In classical mechanics, $V(x)$ is related to the force which acts on a particle changing the value $p(x)$. Alternatively, $V(x-dx)$ is related to the force which creates $p(x)$.

For a stochastic potential yielding k momentum kicks i.e. $V(x)=\text{Sum over } k V(k)\exp(ikx)$, one may ask how to create a momentum p . For a given k , $p-k$ yields p , yet there is a probability associated with having a particle with momentum $p-k$ at x i.e. $P((p-k)/x)$. Thus, $\text{Sum over } k V(k) \exp(ikx) P((p-k)/x)$ is the portion of the potential (weighted by the probabilities to have each $p-k$) and one may associate it with $p^*p/2m P(p/x)$. Thus, a very select portion of the potential is part of a conservation of energy equation with $p^*p/2m P(p/x)$. Interestingly, this potential is evaluated at x even though the creation of p would occur from $x-dx$ to x . Thus, one may consider the sum:

$$\text{Sum over } p \quad p^*p/2m P(p/x) + \text{Sum over } k V(k)\exp(ikx) P((p-k)/x) \quad ((4))$$

The first term is $KE_{ave}(x)$ while $\text{Sum over } p P((p-k)/x)$ is essentially $\text{Sum over } p P(p/x)=1$. Thus, ((4)) is equivalent to:

$$KE_{ave}(x) + V(x) = E \quad ((5)) \text{ If one insists that the average energy at each } x \text{ is } E.$$

The conservation of energy equation pertaining to p is then:

$$p^*p/2m P(p/x) + \text{Sum over } k V(k)\exp(ikx) P((p-k)/x) = E P(p/x) \quad ((6))$$

Dividing by $P(p/x)$ one has an equation with a constant E on the RHS for every p in quantum equilibrium (with flow).

((6)) may be obtained in a different manner. One may take the time-independent Schrodinger equation and express $W(x)$, the wavefunction, and $V(x)$ both as Fourier series and then collect coefficients of $\exp(ipx)$.

((6)) is similar in idea, but not form, to the Maxwell-Boltzmann equation:

$$f(e_i)f(e_j) = f(e_l)f(e_k) \text{ where } e_i+e_j=e_l+e_k \text{ and } \ln(f(e_i)) + \ln(f(e_j)) = e_i+e_j = E \quad ((7))$$

$$\text{Thus, for a single } e_i: \ln(f(e)) = b(p^2/2m + V(x)) \text{ where } b = -1/T \quad ((8))$$

In both cases, a partial momentum probability is related to an energy conservation equation. For the statistical mechanical problem, there is no flow and there are many particles, so one may consider two body scattering at a point x . If there is a potential, $e_i = KE + V(x)$. The point seems to be that ((7)) holds for each E value. ((8)), however, is related to the average energy of the whole system i.e. $.5 T$ (for 1 dimension) where T is temperature.

In a quantum system, there is only one E , the average energy, which holds at each x . In classical statistical mechanics, E is every possible value e_i+e_j . In both cases, the conservation of energy equation for a single p is linked to the overall average energy, bT for the classical case and E for the quantum. Thus, an individual energy of p -probability p equation is "moderated" by the overall average energy.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that if one has a momentum distribution at each x point and a stochastic potential rendering kicks of k momentum i.e. $V(x) = \text{Sum over } k V(k)\exp(ikx)$, then on average there is conservation of energy at each x , namely $KE_{ave}(x) + V(x) = E$ as well as a partial equation for each p : $p^2/2m P(p/x) + \text{Sum over } k V(k)\exp(ikx) P((p-k)/x) = E P(p/x)$ ((6)). Each p is related to the same E in the quantum bound state resonance. In an earlier note, we called this a resonance of cycling. We note the similarity of ((6)) in idea (not form) with the Maxwell-Boltzmann case: $\ln(f(e)) = -[p^2/2m + V(x)]/T$. In both cases, there is an equation linking the probability of p with an energy equation related to p . Furthermore, each energy equation with probability of p is linked to the overall average energy of the system. For the classical statistical mechanical case, there is a link to temperature (which is linked to average energy) and in the quantum case the link is with E .